

EMPLOYEES' PERSPECTIVES ON EMPLOYEE ASSISTANCE PROGRAM FOR STRESS MANAGEMENT

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PURPOSE/PROBLEM

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in health and well-being for all age groups were promoted by the United Nations. This study focuses on employee well-being in terms of mental health. Up to 30% of the working-age population suffers from stress and mental illness globally. Distress, a harmful stress, impacts organizational productivity, turnover, and employee health issues. Workplace stress is not the only source for employees; personal issues can also cause stress, which is sometimes difficult to manage. Employee Assistance Program (EAP) is a well-being promotion program implemented globally. It is an employer-sponsored system that advises employees to help them reduce their stress at work from personal concerns, physical health issues, and work-related problems. Employee Assistance Programs (EAP) intend to provide numerous benefits to both employees and organizations. Employee Assistance Program is effective in many parts of the world, such as North America and Europe, because around 66.2% of employees have experience with the Employee Assistance Program (Roche et al., 2018).

However, in Thailand, only a small number of companies have implemented Employee Assistance Program (EAP). Even though the literature showed that EAP could benefit stress management, Thailand has a greater percentage of workers who suffer from stress than many other countries (Ratanasiripong et al., 2016). Differences in the value of collectivism in Thailand's cultural system vs. countries that have effectively implemented EAP could explain Thailand's employees reluctance to seek professional help for stress management (Hechanova et al., 2020).

The Health Belief Model (HBM) is one theory that explains why people decide to participate in health interventions. Although existing research has shown a relationship between the Health Belief Model (HBM) and the intention to utilize

health services by applying the theory of planned behavior (TPB), there is currently no study in the EAP on demand and user perspectives in Thailand. As a result, the present study underlines the necessity of learning more about employee perceptions of EAP use and the factors influencing their decision and obstacle to use the services. It is important to discover the employee perspective to introduce the Employee Assistance Program to Thai employees in diverse organization cultures, at the very least to identify in-depth solutions to their concerns.

This research is grounded on the Health Belief Model (HBM) (Strecher & Rosenstock, 1997) to investigate why individuals choose to join or not participate in stress management intervention activities when engaging in work distress or their personal lives. The goal is to reduce the likelihood of developing severe mental illnesses and improve the organization's productivity and outcomes. Furthermore, government policy might implement a health promotion program to improve employee well-being on a larger scale. Hence, the research objectives are:

To investigate employees' perspectives on Employee Assistance Program usage intention based on the Health Belief Model (HBM) concept by determining the factors influencing the employee to use the Employee Assistance Program and examine the moderating roles of perceived trust and perceived privacy protection to intention to use the Employee Assistance Program.

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

This study employed the quantitative approach of conducting survey research by purposive sampling on 434 employees in companies where EAP services have been implemented. At the site of the survey, the researcher will contact the company's human resources department to confirm if EAP services are available to employees. According to the Personal Data Protection Act, 2019 Human Resources Department were unable to provide personal information of their employees to the researchers. On the other hand, they can only confirm the Employee Assistance Program availability for the researcher. Descriptive analysis and one-way ANOVA were used to investigate demographic information. The structural equation model will be used to test the hypothesis. Furthermore, Multigroup Analysis is employed to compare the perception of the employee who is familiar with EAP and not familiar with the EAP.

FINDINGS

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The study found that the factors influencing Thai employees to utilize EAP include age, employment status, length of service, and work hours. Based on Health Belief Model, perceived benefits and cues to action positively influence the intention to use an EAP, but self-efficacy negatively impacts the intention to utilize EAP. The extent variables found that perceived privacy protection directly affects the intention to use EAP and strengthens the relationship between self-efficacy and intention to use EAP and weakens the relationship cues to action and perceived barriers and intention to use EAP. Perceived trust does not directly affect the intention to use EAP. However, the results present a positive moderating effect of between perceived severity and self-efficacy toward the intention to use EAP. Additionally, whether employees are familiar with the EAP or not, their perspective toward the EAP does not present significant differences.

Table 1 Demographic Profile of Respondents (n = 434)

Demographics	Catalogue	Frequency	Percentage
Age	18 – 25	59	13.6%
	26 – 30	178	41.0%
	31 – 40	136	31.3%
	41 – 50	47	10.8%
	51 – 60	11	2.5%
	Above 60	3	0.7%
Gender	Male	126	29%
	Female	302	69.6%
	Prefer not to say	6	1.4%
Educational level	Below bachelor's Degree	26	6.0%
	Bachelor's Degree	299	68.9%
	Master's Degree	96	22.1%
	Doctorate Degree	13	3.0%
Marital status	Single	282	65.0%
	Married	141	32.5%
	Divorced/Separated	13	3.0%
	Widowed	3	0.7%
Underlying disease	Yes	81	18.7%
	No	353	81.3%
Region	Northern	1	0.2%
	Northeastern	107	24.7%
	Central	303	69.8%
	Southern	4	0.9%
	Others	19	4.4%
Monthly salary	Below 20,000	90	20.7%
	20,001 – 40,000	220	50.7%
	40,001 – 60,000	56	12.9%
	Above 60,000	68	15.7%

Employment status	Full-time	386	88.9%
	Part-time	6	1.4%
	Contract/Temporary	29	6.7%
	Others	13	3.0%
Duration of service	Least than 1 year	66	15.2%
	1-3 years	130	30.0%
	4-5 years	129	29.7%
	6-10 years	60	13.8%
	11-15 years	13	3.0%
	Above 15 years	36	8.3%
Working hours	Below or equal 40 hours per week	60	13.82%
	41-50 hours per week	171	39.40%
	51-100 per week	196	45.16%
	Above 100 per week	7	1.61%
EAP awareness	Yes	235	54.1%
	No	173	39.9%
	Not sure	26	6.0%
Types of EAP	Internal	59	13.6%
	External	146	33.6%
	Not sure	229	52.3%
Types of EAP	Face to Face	35	8.1%
	Internet	98	22.6%
	Telephone	47	10.8%
	Others	20	4.6%
	Never	234	53.9%
	Total	434	100.00%

Standardized estimates of the proposed model. (All respondents) (N=434)

Hypotheses	Relationship	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Result
Control Variables	Age	-0.129*	0.018	0.017	0.016	
	Gender	0.049	-0.002	-0.026	-0.01	
	Duration of service	0.000	-0.049	-0.028	-0.038	
H1	PSUS → IN		-0.011	0.053	0.009	Rejected
H2	PSEV → IN		0.028	-0.129	-0.032	Rejected
H3	PBF → IN		0.334***	0.309***	0.339***	Supported
H4	PBR → IN		0.015	0.064	0.053	Rejected
H5	SE → IN		-0.066*	-0.114*	-0.108**	Contrasted
H6	CA → IN		0.501***	0.671***	0.559***	Supported
H7	PT → IN		0.041	0.034	-0.018	Rejected
H8	PPP → IN		0.145**	0.107	0.153**	Supported
H1a	PPPxPSUS → IN			-0.159		Rejected
H2a	PPPxPSEV → IN			0.431		Rejected
H3a	PPPxPBF → IN			0.112		Rejected
H4a	PPPxPBR → IN			-0.186*		Contrasted
H5a	PPPxSE → IN			0.195*		Supported
H6a	PPPxCA → IN			-0.401*		Contrasted
H1b	PTxPSUS → IN				-0.071	Rejected
H2b	PTxPSEV → IN				0.203*	Supported
H3b	PTxPBF → IN				0.007	Rejected
H4b	PTxPBR → IN				-0.102	Rejected
H5b	PTxSE → IN				0.124*	Supported
H6b	PTxCA → IN				-0.137	Rejected

Note: P Value <0.001 *** , P Value <0.01 ** P Value <0.05 *

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

This study supports extending the HBM in particular context especially in using EAP for stress management by using perceived privacy protection and perceived trust as moderators. Moreover, the results from this research can possibly be used as a valuable resource for the EAP implementation process in organization practice on how to increase employee well-being to achieve Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In addition, it can enable the academic community to apply theoretical implications to various managerial contexts.

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSION

This research has several limitations, such as this study did not restrict to one particular industry. Collecting data from different industrial can better analyze the information for better results. Moreover, this result should be extended to study in western context or developed countries as the comparative study.

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